

1 **TITLE PAGE**

2 **Title:** Obesity and overweight as risk factors for low back pain in children and adolescents: a
3 meta-analysis

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27 **Authors' contributions**

28 All authors contributed to the conception and design, acquisition, analysis and interpretation of
29 data and drafting of the manuscript. JGM, ICM and AGC carried out the systematic review. JGM
30 and JLL performed the statistical analyses. JGM wrote a first full draft of the manuscript. All
31 authors participated in the critical revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content.

32 All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

33 **ABSTRACT**

34 **BACKGROUND:** Childhood obesity and overweight are associated with musculoskeletal pain, but
35 the association between low back pain (LBP) and overweight/obesity in this population needs
36 clarification. The objective of this meta-analysis is to ascertain the relationship between LBP and
37 obesity/overweight in children and adolescents.

38 **METHODS:** Various databases and specialized journals were queried from inception to October
39 2022. Encompassed were all studies examining the association between overweight or obesity
40 and LBP among participants aged 6 to 18 years. The ROBINS-E tool was employed to assess bias.
41 Random-effects models were used to pool results across studies, with location-scale models
42 used to search for moderator variables where evidence of heterogeneity was found.

43 **RESULTS:** In total, 34 studies were incorporated. Four studies had a low risk of bias, while the
44 remaining studies had some concerns. Nine studies evinced an association between overweight
45 and LBP, in contrast to normal weight, yielding an OR of 1.13 (95% CI 1.10-1.16) and no
46 heterogeneity. Eight studies demonstrated a similar association between obesity and LBP
47 compared to normal weight, with an OR of 1.27 (95% CI 1.20-1.34) and no heterogeneity. Ten
48 studies established an association between overweight/obesity and LBP compared to normal
49 weight, yielding an OR of 1.18 (95% CI 1.14-1.23) and no heterogeneity. Finally, nineteen studies
50 showcased an association between body mass index (BMI) and LBP, with an OR of 1.19 (95% CI
51 1.03-1.39) with evidence of heterogeneity. For this last analysis, we compared the mean BMI in
52 groups and transformed results to log OR, and then retransformed to OR.

53 **CONCLUSION:** Overweight and obesity may be risk factors for LBP in children and adolescents.
54 The association between LBP and obesity appears to be stronger than with overweight.
55 However, the analysis revealed considerable heterogeneity and risk of bias across studies.

56 **Keywords:** Obesity, Overweight, Child, Adolescent, Meta-Analysis, Low back pain

57 **ARTICLE BODY**

58 **INTRODUCTION**

59 Low back pain (LBP) is a common condition among young population and the prevalence and
60 severity are increasing [1,2]. Among healthy children, the estimated point prevalence was 12%,
61 week prevalence 17%, year prevalence reached 33%, and lifetime prevalence 39% [3], and the
62 trajectory of back pain in this population was highly heterogeneous [4]. Young people with LBP
63 often experience a negative impact on their activities of daily living, sport participation and
64 school activities, even leading to school absenteeism [5,6]. Preventing the development of this
65 condition is essential for its management, and the approach to lifestyle habits plays a
66 fundamental role [6]. In addition, identifying and managing LBP in childhood will minimize the
67 impact in adulthood [2]. Modifiable factors should be the focus of attention to promote healthy
68 habits that continue into adulthood [7]. Obesity is a crucial modifiable risk factor in developed
69 countries, with particular importance in childhood, and its prevalence has been steadily
70 improving in recent decades [8,9]. The risk of obesity in childhood has been increased in recent
71 years. In addition, the risks of weight gain can be intensified in the spine, which combined with
72 a lack of muscle strength during growth, low physical activity level, increased sitting time, and
73 psychosocial factors, among others, can lead to the appearance of back pain [10]. Besides, the
74 World Health Organization (WHO) advocates that weight and adiposity control in children and
75 adolescents is essential to improve overall health [11]. One of the most widely used methods
76 for calculating a patient's level of overweight or obesity is the calculation of body mass index
77 (BMI). Although this method does not directly calculate an individual's body fat, it is a commonly
78 used indicator for assessing different health risks due to its ease of use and low cost [12].

79 The potential relationship between weight status and musculoskeletal pain in young people
80 needs to be studied, as it may lead to a vicious circle in which being overweight or obese can
81 lead to musculoskeletal pain, leading to a low level of physical activity that aggravates the pain
82 [13].

83 Although there are meta-analyses [13,14], systematic reviews [10,15], and studies on guidelines
84 and recommendations [16,17] relating obesity and overweight and musculoskeletal pain, the
85 association between obesity and overweight and LBP in children and adolescents remains
86 inconclusive.

87 As the prevalence of obesity, overweight, and LBP continues to rise, and their adverse effects
88 on the health of young individuals become more apparent, it is imperative to conduct a meta-
89 analysis to clarify the relationship between these public health concerns.

90 Therefore, this meta-analysis aimed to quantify the relationship between obesity and
91 overweight and LBP in children and adolescents.

92 **METHODS**

93 **Study design**

94 This meta-analysis was carried out and reported following the Preferred Reporting Items for
95 Systematic Reviews and Meta-analyses (PRISMA) recommendations [18], for more information,
96 see supplementary information (Table 1), and registered with PROSPERO (CRD42022357033).

97 **Eligibility criteria**

98 We included observational studies that examined the association between LBP and obesity and
99 overweight using BMI. Thus, we included studies that associated BMI category (normal weight,
100 overweight and obese) and LBP; those that compared BMI between two groups (those with LBP
101 and those without LBP); and those studies that examined the association between LBP and BMI
102 quantitatively. In those studies where BMI categories were studied, normal weight group should
103 be the reference group. Studies had to be published or completed at the date of the search. No
104 language restrictions were applied. Participants had to be aged between 6 and 18 years. Studies
105 whose sample mostly had LBP due to pathology were excluded. Studies had to report results by

106 analyzing the association between BMI and LBP using odds ratio (OR), relative risk (RR), or the
107 difference of BMI between groups (participants with and without LBP).

108 **Data sources**

109 Different methods were used to search for articles: specialized health science and general
110 databases, journals specialized in the topic, references from experts and citations of included
111 studies. Published and unpublished studies were searched.

112 The different databases were PubMed, Web of Science, SCOPUS, PsycINFO, CENTRAL, PEDro,
113 LILACS, IBECS, and ScienceDirect. The specialist journals reviewed were BMJ and Spine.

114 **Search strategy**

115 The search strategy was carried out from the inception of the databases and journals to October
116 2022, with a combination of the following keywords: “Low back pain”, “back pain”, “backache”,
117 “LBP”, “body mass index”, “BMI”, overweight, obesity, “pediatric obesity”, “paediatric obesity”,
118 “morbid obesity”, “prevalence”, “risk factor”, children, adolescent, teen, youth and school. For
119 more details about the search terms and combinations, see supplementary information (Table
120 2).

121 The search was carried out by one author (JGM) and all authors reviewed and decided which
122 studies were included.

123 **Data extraction**

124 Data extraction from the articles was carried out following a previously elaborated coding
125 manual, so that the two authors who carried out the coding and the third author for the
126 consensus had the same criteria for extracting the information. This manual was based on
127 Lipsey's recommendations [19], and variables were classified into 3 categories: substantive
128 (context, and participant), methodological, and extrinsic variables. For more information, see
129 supplementary information (Table 3).

130 Data from each study were collected separately by two authors (JGM, ICM). To resolve
131 disagreements, a third author (AGC) intervened to decide on the extracted data. Additional data
132 were requested directly from the authors of the collected studies when required.

133 In order to assess the reliability of the coding process, Cohen's Kappa was calculated for
134 qualitative variables and the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC) [20] for quantitative
135 variables. Kappa and ICC values were 1 and hence no intervention by a third author was
136 necessary.

137 **Risk of bias assessment**

138 Risk of bias (RoB) was evaluated using the ROBINS-E tool version 2022 [21], which is specifically
139 designed for observational studies that measure the impact of an exposure. Two authors
140 independently performed the assessment of RoB (JGM and ICM). RoB was evaluated for each of
141 the seven domains individually and then assigned a final rating based on the recommendations
142 provided by the tool authors. The assessment classified RoB as "low", "some concerns", or
143 "high". Inter-rater agreement was measured using Cohen's Kappa, which resulted in a score of
144 1.

145 **Outcome measures**

146 Studies should analyze the association between BMI and LBP – either with numerical variables
147 or categorical ones – or provide sufficient data to analyze it. When BMI was reported by category
148 (e.g., normal weight, overweight, obese), we used the cut-off points considered by the authors
149 of the primary studies.

150 **Effect size index**

151 The studies that examined the relationship between BMI and LBP through various categories
152 utilized the OR to calculate the effect size. In cases where d indices were provided, ORs were

153 prioritized to ensure comparability across studies. The effect measure for the analyses was the
154 log OR (LOR), which was then back-transformed to the ratio scale to facilitate interpretation.

155 The studies comparing the BMI of participants with LBP to those without LBP (for which d indices
156 could be computed) were linked to studies that reported the logistic regression values. In order
157 to facilitate a more comprehensive analysis and increase the reliability of the results, d indices
158 were converted to OR using the formula $LOR = 1.65d$ [22]. This harmonization of indices allowed
159 for the inclusion of a larger number of studies in the analysis, increasing the reliability of the
160 results.

161 The calculation of the effect size was conducted by the first author (JGM) under the supervision
162 of another researcher (JLL).

163 **Data analysis**

164 The calculations were performed using a random-effects model using the correction proposed
165 by Hartung [23]. In order to visually and numerically represent the individual effects of each
166 study and the overall effect, a forest plot with a 95% confidence interval was created.
167 Heterogeneity was assessed using the I^2 index and prediction intervals [24]. When some
168 evidence of heterogeneity was found and the number of studies allowed for it, moderator
169 variable analyses were conducted using categorical variables (ANOVA) and numerical variables
170 using location-scale models, which enable to identify moderators of the outcome size and/or
171 amount of heterogeneity across outcomes [25]. The location-scale model was used to analyze
172 whether study characteristics affect the magnitude of the observed effects (location) and
173 whether the observed effects are more heterogeneous depending on specific features of the
174 primary studies (scale). When studies provided both unadjusted and adjusted data, the adjusted
175 data was used.

176 To assess publication bias, Egger's test and funnel plot were utilized. The statistical analyses
177 were conducted using the R software[26] with the "metafor" package [27]. The PRISMA checklist

178 [18] was utilized to verify the completeness and transparency of the meta-analysis process, for
179 more information, see supplementary information (Table 1).

180 **RESULTS**

181 Out of the initial 13,694 results, 13,686 were found in databases and 8 were from other sources.
182 After removing duplicate entries and carefully reviewing the remaining articles, 99 articles were
183 selected for further examination. Most of the articles were subsequently eliminated due to
184 various reasons, such as not including our variable of interest, insufficient information for
185 statistical analysis, or the inclusion of adult samples. Finally, a total of 35 papers were included
186 in the final analysis [7,28–61]. One study was reported in two papers [44,45], these two papers
187 were counted as one in the analysis. Fig. 1 shows the process of identification and selection of
188 the studies. Three studies were finally excluded because they did not provide sufficient
189 statistical information. [62–64].

190 **Study characteristics**

191 The included studies were published between 1994 and 2021. Twenty-seven studies were cross-
192 sectional studies [7,28–39,41,44–49,52–54,56,57,59,60], six were cohort studies
193 [40,42,43,50,55,61] and two were case-control studies [51,58]. Studies were conducted in
194 several countries, including Brazil [7,33,34,47,48,52], Kuwait [28,36], Iran [29,35,38,56], Spain
195 [30,41], Japan [31,32,37], Colombia [39], Bosnia and Herzegovina [40], Australia [42], Finland
196 [43,61], Portugal [44,45], Germany [46], Switzerland [49,53,55], Israel [50], China [51,54], USA
197 [57], England [58,60] and Greece [59]. Based on the age of participants, six studies were
198 conducted in children [7,29,34,39,41,53], twelve in adolescents [30,33,36,38,43,46,48,50,57–
199 59,61], and seventeen included children and adolescents
200 [28,31,32,35,37,40,42,44,45,47,49,51,52,54–56,60]. Most participants were recruited from
201 educational institutions [7,28,29,33–36,38–41,44,45,47,48,51–57,59–61], others from sports
202 teams [30–32,37,46], from community [42,49,50] and one unspecified [58]. The percentage of

203 male varied from zero percent [38] to hundred percent [55]. Heterogeneity was found with
204 respect to LBP prevalence, with studies reporting LBP lifetime prevalence
205 [33,34,38,41,46,47,49,55], LBP period prevalence [7,28–30,35,36,39,42–45,48,51–
206 54,56,57,60,61], and LBP point prevalence [31,32,37,40,58,59]. The criteria used to categorize
207 participants into groups according to BMI were heterogeneous, using WHO criteria [65] in three
208 studies [28,29,36], International Obesity Task Force criteria [66,67] in seven studies [33,41,43–
209 45,47,48], and Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) criteria [68] in two studies
210 [40,50], and two unspecified [34,52]. The total number of participants in all the studies were
211 859,248. For more information, see Table 1.

212 Regarding the prevalence of LBP, there was significant heterogeneity. For example, in lifetime
213 prevalence, it ranged from 34.74% [55] to 76.97% [33]. Additionally, there was heterogeneity
214 among different BMI subgroups, with a higher prevalence in studies involving adolescents
215 compared to those including only children. Concerning the period prevalence, there was
216 substantial temporal heterogeneity. In one-month prevalence, it varied from 13.1% [52] to
217 39.72% [39], and this prevalence seemed to be higher in studies that exclusively involved
218 children. The one-year prevalence ranged from 18% [35] to 57.36% [48], with a higher
219 prevalence in studies exclusively involving adolescents. Lastly, regarding point prevalence, it
220 ranged from 4.8% in athletes [31] to 22.74% in non-athlete populations [40], up to 50% in non-
221 athlete populations [58]. This prevalence appeared to be higher in studies that solely included
222 adolescents.

223 Concerning the incidence of overweight and obesity in the studies included, it was noted that in
224 all studies except one [28] more than half of the participants had a normal weight. The
225 prevalence of participants with normal weight varied from 43.55% [28] to 90.41% [39].
226 Regarding overweight, the prevalence ranged from 4% [34] to 21.71% [28]. Lastly, the
227 prevalence of obesity ranged from 10.74% [43] to 33.16% [28]. In all studies that reported

228 separate prevalence figures for overweight and obesity, overweight was consistently more
229 prevalent than obesity. Overall, 5.65% with underweight, 77.75% with normal weight, 10.3%
230 with overweight, and 5.82% with obesity. See Table 2 for more information.

231 **Risk of bias**

232 Only four studies [7,30,37,61] were considered to have low risk of bias, while the rest raised
233 some concerns. The articles with low risk of bias in their final assessment obtained this score
234 across all domains. The studies with some concerns obtained a high risk of bias score in domains
235 1A or 1B, and low risk of bias in the remaining domains, following the author's
236 recommendations. Domains 1A and 1B were responsible for evaluating confounding variables,
237 and studies penalized with a high risk of bias failed to adequately control for these variables,
238 and the results from risk of bias assessments directly affect the results reported, as they should
239 be interpreted with caution. For more information, see Table 3.

240 **Mean effect size and heterogeneity analysis**

241 **1) Comparison of normal weight and overweight in association with LBP**

242 Regarding the effect size in the association between overweight and LBP, an overall OR of 1.13
243 (95% CI 1.10-1.16) based on 9 studies was obtained, with no evidence of heterogeneity ($\tau^2 = 0$),
244 suggesting slightly higher odds of LBP among overweight children and adolescents. To calculate
245 the effect size, the Minghelli 2015 [44] and 2014 [45] papers were combined. Fig. 2a displays the
246 forest plot, presenting all the included studies and the average effect size. All nine studies
247 [28,33,34,36,39,40,44,45,50,52] included in this analysis reported an individual OR of 1 or
248 higher, with the study by dos Santos et al. [34] standing out with an OR of 4 (95% CI 0.13-122.74).
249 The effect size was driven by Hershkovich al. [50], which was the only one to reach a significant
250 individual OR. Importantly, this study covered a substantial sample size of 712296 participants,
251 with a weight of 95.28% of the total effect size. Consequently, a sensitivity analysis was
252 conducted, excluding this study from the calculation. The removal of this study resulted in a

253 reduction of the effect size, yielding an OR of 1.11 (95% CI 0.96-1.27, $\tau^2=0$). In order to assess
254 the robustness of the findings, a second sensitivity analysis was conducted by excluding the
255 study conducted by dos Santos et al. [34] due to its substantial effect size. The effect size
256 remained unchanged in this re-analysis, consistent with the first analysis, yielding a value of OR=
257 1.13 (95% CI 1.10-1.15, $\tau^2=0$).

258 Four studies [28,36,39,52] presented their ORs, while the ORs for the remaining studies were
259 manually calculated from the 2x2 table frequencies. The studies that provided the OR
260 designated the normal weight group as the reference category. To calculate the OR using this
261 method, it was necessary for the normal weight and overweight groups to be well-defined. The
262 total sample size across all studies included in this analysis amounted to 716297 participants.

263 To evaluate publication bias, the Egger's test and funnel plot were utilized. The results revealed
264 a non-significant finding with a p-value of 0.58, indicating the absence of publication bias. Fig.
265 2b visually depicts the funnel plot, providing further support for the absence of publication bias.

266 **2) Comparison of normal weight and obesity in association with LBP**

267 Eight studies [28,33,36,40,43–45,50,52] were included in this analysis to evaluate the effect size
268 in the association between obesity and LBP. The overall effect estimate was OR=1.27 (95% CI
269 1.20-1.34), with no evidence of heterogeneity ($\tau^2 = 0$), suggesting higher odds of LBP among
270 children and adolescents with obesity. Three studies [33,36,52] reported an OR lower than 1. As
271 well as to the previous analysis, the two papers by Minghelli et al. [44,45] were considered as a
272 single study. The forest plot in Fig. 3a presents the comprehensive analysis of all the included
273 studies and the final effect size. Among the included studies, only the study conducted by
274 Hershkovich et al. [50], which boasted the largest sample size of 675089 participants, achieved
275 statistical significance in its individual analysis. This study, as the previous comparison, carried
276 significant weight in determining the final effect size, contributing to 90.94% of the total.

277 Consequently, a sensitivity analysis was conducted, involving the exclusion of this study,
278 resulting in a reduction of the effect size to OR = 1.10 (95%CI 0.97-1.24).

279 Only three studies [28,36,52] provided the OR with normal weight as the reference group, while
280 the remaining studies reported the raw counts in 2x2 tables. The combined sample size of all
281 studies included in this analysis amounted to 682512 participants.

282 Moreover, the presence of publication bias was assessed using the Egger's test and funnel plot.
283 The results indicated a statistically significant finding with a p-value of 0.037, highlighting the
284 need to consider publication bias, as depicted in Fig. 3b.

285 **3) Comparison of normal weight and overweight-obesity in association with LBP**

286 The association between combined overweight/obesity and LBP was also calculated, including
287 ten studies [29,33,40,41,44,45,47,48,50,52,60] that provided such comparison. The overall
288 effect size was OR=1.18 (95% CI 1.14-1.23), with no evidence of heterogeneity ($\tau^2 = 0$),
289 suggesting slightly higher odds of LBP among children and adolescents with overweight and
290 obesity, compared to their counterparts with body weight considered as normal. Consistent with
291 previous analyses, the two papers by Minghelli et al. [44,45] were considered as a single study.
292 The forest plot in Fig. 4a displays the overall effect size and contributions of each study. Among
293 the included studies, only two studies [29,52] reported an OR below 1, and only the study by
294 Hershkovich et al. [50] achieved statistical significance in its individual analysis, which had the
295 largest sample size of 758487 participants and contributed to 94.39% of the overall effect size.
296 To assess the robustness of the findings, a sensitivity analysis was conducted excluding this study
297 from the analysis. As a result, the effect size was reduced to OR = 1.16 (95%CI 0.99-1.36).

298 For this analysis, only three studies [41,47,60] provided the ORs with normal weight as the
299 reference group, while the remaining studies reported 2x2 tables with the information to
300 calculate them. The total sample size across all studies was 766,257 participants. One study [60]
301 categorized weight groups based on BMI thresholds of ≤ 25 and > 25 . Despite this unconventional

302 categorization, it was included in the analysis since the lower limit did not extend below normal
303 weight and the upper limit reached into the range of obesity categories. In addition, only one
304 study provided adjusted OR data (adjusted for unspecified socioeconomics variables) [47].

305 The result of the Egger's test and funnel plot showed no statistically significant findings with a
306 p-value of 0.50. This suggests an absence of publication bias (Fig. 4b).

307 **4) BMI and LBP association**

308 The association between BMI and LBP was examined in 19 studies [7,30–
309 32,35,37,38,42,46,49,51,53–59,61], which ultimately resulted in 21 analyses as one study
310 provided three independent group comparisons [31]. Eight studies reported the OR from logistic
311 regression in their articles [31,32,37,49,53,56,59,61], and eleven studies provided the BMI
312 values of participants with and without LBP [7,30,35,38,42,46,51,54,55,57,58]. By combining all
313 these studies, we obtained the 21 analyses. The adaptation of these 21 results to a common
314 index (log OR) allows us to analyze them as a whole and obtain more robust results.

315 The overall effect size was 1.19 (95%CI 1.03-1.39), with strong evidence of heterogeneity ($I^2 =$
316 98.51 , $\tau^2 = 0.06$, 95% PI 0.70 to 2.04). The forest plot in Fig. 5a visually represents the combined
317 effect size as well as the individual contributions of each study towards the overall analysis.
318 Seven studies obtained significant values supporting the association between the two variables
319 [38,42,46,51,54,55,58], while the rest did not. One study yielded a highly negative value without
320 statistical significance [57]. It was observed that most articles providing their data through OR
321 and logistic regression did not find an association. On the other hand, articles that compared the
322 BMI of participants with and without LBP showed a tendency towards association. Due to the
323 heterogeneity of including studies that provided the OR with studies that provided the mean
324 difference, a sensitivity analysis was performed including only the eight studies (ten analysis)
325 that provided the OR with a reduction of the effect size to OR 1.06 (95% CI 1.01-1.10).

326 Adjusted and unadjusted results were included in this analysis. Adjustment of results was only
327 found in 3 studies, with low consensus on the variables that should be adjusted for in the analysis
328 of this variable, including gender, age, BMI, level of sports equipment and number of training
329 days per week [37], carrying the school bag on one shoulder only [59] and adjusted for all
330 variables included in the study (sitting height, BMI, growth of BMI, kyphosis, increase of
331 kyphosis, and hump size) [61]. The three studies that included adjusted data joined the other
332 studies that did not provide adjusted data for the overall analysis and their effect sizes were
333 non-significant in all cases. However, there were no notable differences in effect size compared
334 to other studies that provided unadjusted data.

335 Five studies provided data from participants engaged in competitive sports, specifically
336 equestrianism [30], judo, karate and kendo [31], volleyball [32], baseball [37], and athletics [46].
337 Among these, only athletics showed a significant association. The study by Yabe et al. 2020a [31]
338 divided its participants based on the sport they engaged in and provided separate ORs for each
339 group, which were analyzed separately.

340 The Egger's test yielded a result of $p=0.67$, indicating that there is no risk of publication bias.
341 Additionally, the funnel plot was generated and no asymmetry was observed (Fig. 5b).

342 **Analyzing moderator variables**

343 Given the evidence of heterogeneity found in the last meta-analysis, moderator analyses were
344 carried out with the aim to better understand the heterogeneity among the 21 effect sizes
345 included. To analyze the age group variable and considering the distribution of participants, the
346 most suitable comparison was between children and adolescents versus adolescents alone. The
347 location-scale model revealed no association between the age group and the magnitude of the
348 effect estimates ($\hat{\beta} = 0.21$, 95% CI: -0.461 to 0.892, without statistical significance. Conversely,
349 the scale coefficient yielded a marginally significant effect, ($\hat{\alpha} = -1.347$, 95% CI: -2.813 to 0.117,

350 p=0.07, suggesting that the heterogeneity was lower in the group of adolescents compared to
351 the group that included adolescents and children.

352 Regarding percentage of males, the location part of the model showed no evidence of an
353 association with the magnitude of the effect estimates ($\hat{\beta} = 0.004$, 95% CI: -0.003 to 0.012),
354 whereas the scale part provided evidence of more heterogeneous results among studies with
355 more females ($\hat{\alpha}=-0.033$, 95% CI: -0.047 to -0.018).

356

357 **DISCUSSION**

358 A systematic review with meta-analysis was conducted to determine the association between
359 obesity, overweight, and LBP. The physiological relationship between BMI and LBP is undeniable,
360 as the lumbar region supports the entire weight of the back, which, combined with the growth
361 changes that occur during childhood and adolescence, makes it a susceptible area for pain [10].
362 In fact, systematic reviews attempting to establish a relationship between weight and LBP have
363 been conducted, but the conclusions have been inconclusive [10,15]. Regarding meta-analyses,
364 one demonstrated that overweight and obesity are associated with comorbidities [14], and only
365 one specifically focused on overweight and LBP. This meta-analysis yielded an effect size of
366 RR=1.42 (95% CI 1.03–1.97). However, due to the low number of studies, potential publication
367 bias, and high heterogeneity among the studies, the authors concluded that there is low-quality
368 evidence and the results should be interpreted as such. Additionally, this meta-analysis included
369 a study with an effect size of RR = 14.39 (95%CI 1.98-104.66) [69], and no sensitivity analysis was
370 performed to assess whether the effects remained consistent without this study. This study was
371 not included in our meta-analysis because it did not specify that the pathology under study was
372 LBP, but rather BP. Since the present study exclusively focuses on LBP, this study was excluded.
373 As for the variable of overweight, our meta-analysis obtained an OR= 1.13 (95% CI 1.10-1.16),
374 which is very similar to the findings of this study. However, when excluding the study by

375 Hershkovich et al. [50], the effect size decreased to OR=1.11 (95% CI 0.96-1.27) eliminating
376 statistical significance. No previous meta-analysis has examined the association between obesity
377 and LBP or between overweight/obesity and LBP.

378 As mentioned before, in our analyses of overweight, obesity, and overweight/obesity with LBP,
379 the study by Hershkovich et al. [50] carries the most weight in the final effect size due to its large
380 sample size. Sensitivity analyses determined a lack of association between the variables
381 analyzed once this influential study was removed, and the minimal or absent heterogeneity in
382 the analyses demonstrates a tendency towards a small association. While it is true that such
383 large studies can distort the results for other studies, the risk of bias in this study is considered
384 to be "some concerns", similar to the majority of the other studies. Our findings highlight a need
385 for more robust studies to be conducted in this field, so that future evidence synthesis efforts
386 can draw more solid conclusions.

387 We found heterogeneity in the types of studies included (cross-sectional, case-controls and
388 cohorts) to investigate the association between variables. Due to the limited number of studies,
389 we had to mix the different types of studies by converting the effect size of each study into a
390 common metric in order to group them together, although methodologically correct, it would
391 have been more accurate to find as many cohorts and case-control studies as possible with low
392 risk of bias and with a large analysis of the moderator variables. Furthermore, the
393 transformation formula used to convert d values into LOR values is based on some assumptions
394 that might not always be met in practice, leading to potential bias in the resulting estimates.

395 Furthermore, there is considerable heterogeneity in classifying individuals as having normal
396 weight, overweight, and obesity. In this meta-analysis, studies were included that categorized
397 their participants based on BMI using criteria from the WHO [65], International Obesity Task
398 Force [66,67], or CDC [68]. Although these criteria are very similar, and it is unlikely that there
399 would be significant differences in the composition of participants in each group, greater

400 homogeneity among the research community would be desirable. By conducting separate
401 analyses for overweight and obesity, this study enables us to explore whether the transition
402 from normal weight to overweight or from overweight to obesity results in a notable increase
403 in the association. Specifically, the association between LBP and obesity appears to be stronger
404 than that with overweight.

405 The heterogeneity observed in the included articles was also reflected in the study population
406 itself, given the inclusion of children and adolescents. Due to information limitations, age was
407 analyzed, when feasible, as a moderating variable to account for the association degree across
408 different age groups. Studies conducted on participants involved in sports were included,
409 contributing to increased heterogeneity among them. However, due to limited information,
410 analyses comparing participants engaged in sports with those who were not were not feasible.
411 It would have been particularly insightful to examine the level of sports engagement
412 (competitive or high level), however, studies did not furnish this information.

413 Children were predominantly sourced from school environments and through schools or entire
414 classes. Generally, information regarding LBP assessment relied on self-report, and BMI was
415 determined by the respective authors of each study. Regarding the prevalence in the studies,
416 there was also heterogeneity, with some studies providing lifetime prevalence of LBP, while
417 others focused on the last few months or point prevalence. This diversity further complicated
418 the analysis of associations, as pinpointing the association amidst such heterogeneity proved
419 challenging. It would also have been interesting if data on previous injuries or previous episodes
420 of LBP had been reported, but this information was not provided in the studies.

421 The heterogeneity found in the prevalence range deserves to be taken into account. We found
422 from lifetime prevalence to point prevalence, thus, longer periods may capture chronic or
423 recurring cases, while shorter durations may highlight acute or transient occurrences, however,
424 a longer period may help to better analyze and understand certain confounding variables.

425 Moreover, it would have been interesting to explore other moderating variables that could
426 potentially influence the effect size, such as sitting time or engagement in physical activities.
427 Although these variables were included in the analysis, the limited number of studies available
428 did not allow for conclusive results. Therefore, it is recommended that future scientific articles
429 incorporate this information to further enhance our understanding of this pathology.

430 The study has numerous strengths. Firstly, it conducted a comprehensive search of both
431 published and unpublished articles, ensuring that all available information on the topic was
432 considered. This thorough search yielded a total of 35 articles and involved a substantial number
433 of participants, enhancing the study's robustness. Secondly, to ensure accuracy and reliability,
434 two authors independently extracted data from the selected studies and applied a risk of bias
435 tool. Furthermore, this study is particularly noteworthy as it was the first meta-analysis
436 exclusively focusing on LBP in children and adolescents, and provided substantial knowledge on
437 this topic. However, it is important to acknowledge the limitations of the study. Firstly, many of
438 the articles included in the analysis exhibited some concerns regarding the risk of bias.

439 Additionally, significant heterogeneity was observed in relation to the tool used to categorize
440 the BMI category of participants, in the population studied (children, adolescents, athletes), in
441 the types of study (cohorts, case-controls, and cross-sectional, with very different prevalence
442 studied (lifetime, period and point prevalence), and it is noteworthy to consider the possibility
443 that the effect size reported in the study may have been driven by the results of a particular
444 study.

445 **CONCLUSION**

446 Overweight and obesity may be risk factors for LBP in children and adolescents. The association
447 between LBP and obesity appears to be stronger than the association with overweight.
448 However, the analysis revealed considerable heterogeneity between the various studies, which
449 were mostly assessed to have moderate risk of bias. In particular, these studies often did not

450 take into account confounding factors that could influence the effect size. Consequently, it is
451 imperative to approach the observed results with caution, emphasizing the need for careful
452 interpretation due to these inherent limitations.

453 **Conflict of interest statement**

454 The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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481 **REFERENCES**

- 482 1. Mallow GM, Zepeda D, Kuzel TG, Barajas JN, Aboushaala K, Nolte MT, et al. ISSLS PRIZE in
483 Clinical Science 2022: Epidemiology, risk factors and clinical impact of juvenile Modic
484 changes in paediatric patients with low back pain. *Eur Spine J.* 2022 May 1;31(5):1069–
485 79.
- 486 2. Hwang J, Louie PK, Phillips FM, An HS, Samartzis D. Low back pain in children: a rising
487 concern. *Eur Spine J Off Publ Eur Spine Soc Eur Spinal Deform Soc Eur Sect Cerv Spine Res*
488 *Soc.* 2019 Feb;28(2):211–3.
- 489 3. Calvo-Munoz I, Gomez-Conesa A, Sanchez-Meca J. Prevalence of low back pain in
490 children and adolescents: a meta-analysis. *Bmc Pediatr.* 2013 Jan 26;13:14.
- 491 4. Hebert JJ, Beynon AM, Jones BL, Wang C, Shrier I, Hartvigsen J, et al. Spinal pain in
492 childhood: prevalence, trajectories, and diagnoses in children 6 to 17 years of age. *Eur J*
493 *Pediatr.* 2022 Apr;181(4):1727–36.
- 494 5. O’Sullivan P, Smith A, Beales D, Straker L. Understanding Adolescent Low Back Pain From
495 a Multidimensional Perspective: Implications for Management. *J Orthop Sports Phys*
496 *Ther.* 2017 Oct;47(10):741–51.
- 497 6. Minghelli B. Low back pain in childhood and adolescence phase: consequences,
498 prevalence and risk factors - a revision. *J Spine.* 2017 Jan 1;06:351.
- 499 7. Santos EDS, Bernardes JM, Noll M, Gómez-Salgado J, Ruiz-Frutos C, Dias A. Prevalence of
500 Low Back Pain and Associated Risks in School-Age Children. *Pain Manag Nurs.* 2021 Aug
501 1;22(4):459–64.
- 502 8. Akbari H, Mohammadi M. The Prevalence of Obesity in Iranian Children: A Systematic
503 Review and Meta-analysis. *J Pediatr Rev.* 2022 Apr 10;10(2):93–102.
- 504 9. Kumari S, Shukla S, Acharya S. Childhood Obesity: Prevalence and Prevention in Modern
505 Society. *Cureus.* 2022 Nov;14(11):e31640.
- 506 10. Onan D, Ulger O. Investigating the Relationship between Body Mass Index and Pain in the
507 Spine in Children or Adolescents: A Systematic Review. *Child Obes Print.* 2021
508 Mar;17(2):86–99.
- 509 11. Bull FC, Al-Ansari SS, Biddle S, Borodulin K, Buman MP, Cardon G, et al. World Health
510 Organization 2020 guidelines on physical activity and sedentary behaviour. *Br J Sports*
511 *Med.* 2020 Dec;54(24):1451–62.
- 512 12. Ghesmaty Sangachin M, Cavuoto LA, Wang Y. Use of various obesity measurement and
513 classification methods in occupational safety and health research: a systematic review of
514 the literature. *BMC Obes.* 2018 Nov 1;5(1):28.
- 515 13. Paulis WD, Silva S, Koes BW, van Middelkoop M. Overweight and obesity are associated
516 with musculoskeletal complaints as early as childhood: a systematic review. *Obes Rev.*
517 2014;15(1):52–67.

- 518 14. Sharma V, Coleman S, Nixon J, Sharples L, Hamilton-Shield J, Rutter H, et al. A systematic
519 review and meta-analysis estimating the population prevalence of comorbidities in
520 children and adolescents aged 5 to 18 years. *Obes Rev.* 2019;20(10):1341–9.
- 521 15. Smith S, Sumar B, Dixon K. Musculoskeletal pain in overweight and obese children. *Int J*
522 *Obes* 2005. 2014 Jan;38(1):11–5.
- 523 16. Kumar S, Kelly AS. Review of Childhood Obesity: From Epidemiology, Etiology, and
524 Comorbidities to Clinical Assessment and Treatment. *Mayo Clin Proc.* 2017 Feb
525 1;92(2):251–65.
- 526 17. Frosch M, Mauritz MD, Bielack S, Blödt S, Dirksen U, Dobe M, et al. Etiology, Risk Factors,
527 and Diagnosis of Back Pain in Children and Adolescents: Evidence- and Consensus-Based
528 Interdisciplinary Recommendations. *Child Basel Switz.* 2022 Feb 2;9(2):192.
- 529 18. Page MJ, McKenzie JE, Bossuyt PM, Boutron I, Hoffmann TC, Mulrow CD, et al. Updating
530 guidance for reporting systematic reviews: development of the PRISMA 2020 statement.
531 *J Clin Epidemiol.* 2021 Feb 9;134:103–12.
- 532 19. Lipsey MW. Identifying interesting variables and analysis opportunities. In: *The handbook*
533 *of research synthesis and meta-analysis* 3rd ed. 3rd ed. New York: Russell Sage
534 Foundation; 2019. p. 141–51.
- 535 20. Orwin RG, Vevea JL. Evaluating coding decisions. In: *The handbook of research synthesis*
536 *and meta-analysis*, 2nd ed. New York, NY, US: Russell Sage Foundation; 2009. p. 177–203.
- 537 21. ROBINS-E Development Group (Higgins J, Morgan R, Rooney A, Taylor K, Thayer K, Silva R,
538 Lemeris C, Akl A, Arroyave W, Bateson T, Berkman N, Demers P, Forastiere F, Glenn B,
539 Hróbjartsson A, Kirrane E, LaKind J, Luben T, Lunn R, McAleenan A, McGuinness L,
540 Meerpohl J, Mehta S, Nachman R, Obbagy J, O’Connor A, Radke E, Savović J, Schubauer-
541 Berigan M, Schwingl P, Schunemann H, Shea B, Steenland K, Stewart T, Straif K, Tilling K,
542 Verbeek V, Vermeulen R, Viswanathan M, Zahm S, Sterne J). Risk Of Bias In Non-
543 randomized Studies - of Exposure (ROBINS-E). Launch version, 1 June 2022. Available
544 from: <https://www.riskofbias.info/welcome/robins-e-tool>.
- 545 22. Hedges LV, Olkin I. *Statistical Methods for Meta-Analysis*. Elsevier Science; 1985. 400 p.
- 546 23. Hartung J. An Alternative Method for Meta-Analysis. *Biom J.* 1999;41(8):901–16.
- 547 24. Higgins JPT, Thompson SG, Deeks JJ, Altman DG. Measuring inconsistency in meta-
548 analyses. *BMJ.* 2003 Sep 6;327(7414):557–60.
- 549 25. Viechtbauer W, López-López JA. Location-scale models for meta-analysis. *Res Synth*
550 *Methods.* 2022;13(6):697–715.
- 551 26. R Core Team. *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*. R Foundation for
552 Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>. 2022.
- 553 27. Viechtbauer W. Conducting Meta-Analyses in R with the metafor Package. *J Stat Softw.*
554 2010 Aug 5;36(1):1–48.
- 555 28. Al-Taiair A, Rahman A, Al-Sabah R, Shaban L, AlBaloul AH, Banaee S, et al. Vitamin D levels
556 in relation to low back pain during adolescence. *Br J Nutr.* 2020 Jun 14;123(11):1302–11.

- 557 29. Rezapur-Shahkolai F, Gheysvandi E, Tapak L, Dianat I, Karimi-Shahanjarini A,
558 Heidarmoghdam R. Risk factors for low back pain among elementary school students in
559 western Iran using penalized logistic regression. *Epidemiol Health*. 2020;42:1–9.
- 560 30. Cejudo A, Gines-Diaz A, Rodriguez-Ferran O, Santonja-Medina F, Sainz de Baranda P.
561 Trunk Lateral Flexor Endurance and Body Fat: Predictive Risk Factors for Low Back Pain in
562 Child Equestrian Athletes. *Child-Basel*. 2020 Oct;7(10):172.
- 563 31. Yabe Y, Hagiwara Y, Sekiguchi T, Momma H, Tsuchiya M, Kanazawa K, et al. Low Back Pain
564 in School-Aged Martial Arts Athletes in Japan: A Comparison among Judo, Kendo, and
565 Karate. *Tohoku J Exp Med*. 2020 Aug;251(4):295–301.
- 566 32. Yabe Y, Hagiwara Y, Sekiguchi T, Momma H, Tsuchiya M, Kanazawa K, et al. Association
567 between lower back pain and lower extremity pain among young volleyball players: A
568 cross-sectional study. *Phys Ther Sport*. 2020 May;43:65–9.
- 569 33. Schwertner DS, Oliveira RANS, Koerich MHAL, Motta AF, Pimenta AL, Gioda FR.
570 Prevalence of low back pain in young Brazilians and associated factors: Sex, physical
571 activity, sedentary behavior, sleep and body mass index. *J Back Musculoskelet Rehabil*.
572 2019;33(2):233–44.
- 573 34. dos Santos MA, Lunkes LC, de Oliveira Ribeiro A, de Castro Souza A. Low back pain and
574 risk factors during the third infancy [Dor lombar e os fatores de risco associados durante
575 a terceira infância]. *Fisioter Em Mov*. 2019;32.
- 576 35. Aghilinejad M, Mohammadi S, Bahrami A, Ahmadi, Amini M, Kabir E, et al. The Role of
577 School Backpack and Training Habits on Development of Spinal Pain among Iranian
578 Primary Student. *Iran J Health Saf Environ*. 2019 Spring;6(2):1249–53.
- 579 36. Akbar F, AlBesharah M, Al-Baghli J, Bulbul F, Mohammad D, Qadoura B, et al. Prevalence
580 of low Back pain among adolescents in relation to the weight of school bags. *BMC*
581 *Musculoskelet Disord*. 2019 Jan 22;20(1):37.
- 582 37. Yabe Y, Hagiwara Y, Sekiguchi T, Momma H, Tsuchiya M, Kuroki K, et al. Knee pain is
583 associated with lower back pain in young baseball players: a cross-sectional study. *Knee*
584 *Surg Sports Traumatol Arthrosc*. 2019;27(3):985–90.
- 585 38. Noormohammadpour P, Borghei A, Mirzaei S, Mansournia MA, Ghayour-Najafabadi M,
586 Kordi M, et al. The Risk Factors of Low Back Pain in Female High School Students. *Spine*.
587 2019 Mar 15;44(6):E357–65.
- 588 39. Angarita-Fonseca A, Boneth-Collante M, Ariza-Garcia CL, Parra-Patiño J, Corredor-Vargas
589 JD, Villamizar-Niño AP. Factors associated with non-specific low back pain in children
590 aged 10-12 from Bucaramanga, Colombia: A cross-sectional study. *J Back Musculoskelet*
591 *Rehabil*. 2019;32(5):739–47.
- 592 40. Azabagic S, Pranjić N. The Site of Musculoskeletal Pain in School Children with Excessive
593 Body Weight and Obesity in Bosnia and Herzegovina. *Mater Socio-Medica*. 2019
594 Jun;31(2):88–92.
- 595 41. Muntaner-Mas A, Palou P, Ortega FB, Vidal-Conti J. Sports participation and low back
596 pain in schoolchildren. *J Back Musculoskelet Rehabil*. 2018;31(5):811–9.

- 597 42. Smith A, Beales D, O'Sullivan P, Bear N, Straker L. Low Back Pain With Impact at 17 Years
598 of Age Is Predicted by Early Adolescent Risk Factors From Multiple Domains: Analysis of
599 the Western Australian Pregnancy Cohort (Raine) Study. *J Orthop Sports Phys Ther.* 2017
600 Oct;47(10):752–62.
- 601 43. Mikkonen P, Heikkala E, Paananen M, Remes J, Taimela S, Auvinen J, et al. Accumulation
602 of psychosocial and lifestyle factors and risk of low back pain in adolescence: a cohort
603 study. *Eur Spine J.* 2016;25(2):635–42.
- 604 44. Minghelli B, Oliveira R, Nunes C. Association of obesity with chronic disease and
605 musculoskeletal factors. *Rev Assoc Med Bras.* 2015 Aug;61(4):347–54.
- 606 45. Minghelli B, Oliveira R, Nunes C. Non-specific low back pain in adolescents from the
607 south of Portugal: prevalence and associated factors. *J Orthop Sci.* 2014 Nov;19(6):883–
608 92.
- 609 46. Schmidt CP, Zwingenberger S, Walther A, Reuter U, Kasten P, Seifert J, et al. Prevalence
610 of low back pain in adolescent athletes - an epidemiological investigation. *Int J Sports
611 Med.* 2014 Jul;35(8):684–9.
- 612 47. Graup S, de Araújo Bergmann ML, Bergmann GG. Prevalence of nonspecific lumbar pain
613 and associated factors among adolescents in Uruguaiana, state of Rio Grande do Sul. *Rev
614 Bras Ortop.* 2014;49(6):661–7.
- 615 48. Silva MROGCM, Badaró AFV, Dall'Agnol MM. Low back pain in adolescent and associated
616 factors: A cross sectional study with schoolchildren. *Braz J Phys Ther.* 2014
617 Oct;18(5):402–9.
- 618 49. Wirth B, Knecht C, Humphreys K. Spine Day 2012: spinal pain in Swiss school children-
619 epidemiology and risk factors. *BMC Pediatr.* 2013 Oct 5;13:159.
- 620 50. Hershkovich O, Friedlander A, Gordon B, Arzi H, Derazne E, Tzur D, et al. Associations of
621 body mass index and body height with low back pain in 829,791 adolescents. *Am J
622 Epidemiol.* 2013 Aug 15;178(4):603–9.
- 623 51. Yao W, Luo C, Ai F, Chen Q. Risk Factors for Nonspecific Low-Back Pain in Chinese
624 Adolescents: A Case-Control Study. *Pain Med.* 2012 May;13(5):658–64.
- 625 52. Onofrio AC, da Silva MC, Domingues MR, Rombaldi AJ. Acute low back pain in high school
626 adolescents in Southern Brazil: prevalence and associated factors. *Eur Spine J.* 2012
627 Jul;21(7):1234–40.
- 628 53. Erne C, Elfering A. Low back pain at school: unique risk deriving from unsatisfactory grade
629 in maths and school-type recommendation. *Eur Spine J.* 2011 Dec;20(12):2126–33.
- 630 54. Yao W, Mai X, Luo C, Ai F, Chen Q. A cross-sectional survey of nonspecific low back pain
631 among 2083 schoolchildren in China. *Spine.* 2011 Oct 15;36(22):1885–90.
- 632 55. Balague F, Bibbo E, Melot C, Szpalski M, Gunzburg R, Keller TS. The association between
633 isoinertial trunk muscle performance and low back pain in male adolescents. *Eur Spine J.*
634 2010 Apr;19(4):624–32.

- 635 56. Mohseni-Bandpei MA, Bagheri-Nesami M, Shayesteh-Azar M. Nonspecific low back pain
636 in 5000 Iranian school-age children. *J Pediatr Orthop*. 2007 Mar;27(2):126–9.
- 637 57. Chiang HY, Jacobs K, Orsmond G. Gender-age environmental associates of middle school
638 students' low back pain. *Work*. 2006;26(2):197–206.
- 639 58. Jones MA, Stratton G, Reilly T, Unnithan VB. Biological risk indicators for recurrent non-
640 specific low back pain in adolescents. *Br J Sports Med*. 2005 Mar;39(3):137–40.
- 641 59. Korovessis P, Koureas G, Zacharatos S, Papazisis Z. Backpacks, back pain, sagittal spinal
642 curves and trunk alignment in adolescents: a logistic and multinomial logistic analysis.
643 *Spine*. 2005 Jan 15;30(2):247–55.
- 644 60. Watson KD, Papageorgiou AC, Jones GT, Taylor S, Symmons DPM, Silman AJ, et al. Low
645 back pain in schoolchildren: The role of mechanical and psychosocial factors. *Arch Dis
646 Child*. 2003 Jan;88(1):12–7.
- 647 61. Nissinen M, Heliövaara M, Seitsamo J, Alaranta H, Poussa M. Anthropometric
648 measurements and the incidence of low back pain in a cohort of pubertal children. *Spine*.
649 1994 Jun 15;19(12):1367–70.
- 650 62. Heikkala E, Karppinen J, Mikkola I, Hagnäs M, Oura P. Association Between Family History
651 of Surgically Treated Low Back Pain and Adolescent Low Back Pain. *Spine*. 2022 May
652 1;47(9):649–55.
- 653 63. Lemes IR, Oliveira CB, Silva GCR, Pinto RZ, Tebar WR, Christofaro DG. Association of
654 sedentary behavior and early engagement in physical activity with low back pain in
655 adolescents: a cross-sectional epidemiological study. *Eur Spine J*. 2022 Jan;31(1):152–8.
- 656 64. Martinez-Romero MT, Cejudo A, Sainz de Baranda P. Prevalence and Characteristics of
657 Back Pain in Children and Adolescents from the Region of Murcia (Spain): ISQUIOS
658 Programme. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2022 Jan;19(2):946.
- 659 65. de Onis M, Onyango AW, Borghi E, Siyam A, Nishida C, Siekmann J. Development of a
660 WHO growth reference for school-aged children and adolescents. *Bull World Health
661 Organ*. 2007 Sep;85(9):660–7.
- 662 66. Cole TJ, Bellizzi MC, Flegal KM, Dietz WH. Establishing a standard definition for child
663 overweight and obesity worldwide: international survey. *BMJ*. 2000 May
664 6;320(7244):1240–3.
- 665 67. Cole TJ, Lobstein T. Extended international (IOTF) body mass index cut-offs for thinness,
666 overweight and obesity. *Pediatr Obes*. 2012 Aug;7(4):284–94.
- 667 68. Growth Charts - Clinical Growth Charts [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2023 Jun 1]. Available
668 from: https://www.cdc.gov/growthcharts/clinical_charts.htm
- 669 69. de Sá Pinto AL, de Barros Holanda PM, Radu AS, Villares SMF, Lima FR. Musculoskeletal
670 findings in obese children. *J Paediatr Child Health*. 2006 Jun;42(6):341–4.

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673 **Figures Legends:**

674 **Fig 1.** PRISMA flow diagram.

675 **Fig 2.** Overweight and LBP association forest plot and funnel plot. Forest plot (a); and funnel plot
676 (b).

677 **Fig 3.** Obese and LBP association forest plot and funnel plot. Forest plot (a); and funnel plot (b).

678 **Fig 4.** Overweight-obesity and LBP association forest plot and funnel plot. Forest plot (a); and
679 funnel plot (b).

680 **Fig 5.** BMI and LBP association forest plot and funnel plot. Forest plot (a); and funnel plot (b).

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682 **Table Legends:**

683 **Table 1.** Characteristics of the studies.

684 **Table 2.** Prevalence of body mass index categories, prevalence of low back pain, and effect size.

685 **Table 3.** Risk of bias assessment.

Table 1. Characteristics of the studies.

Study	Design	Country	Number of participants	Age category	% Male	BMI category diagnostic method	Source	Type of prevalence	Period prevalence (months)
Santos 2021 [7]	Cross-sectional	Brazil	377	Children	49	NA	Educational institution	Period	1
Al-Taiar 2020 [28]	Cross-sectional	Kuwait	760	Mixed	50.66	WHO	Educational institution	Period	6
Rezapur-Shahkolai 2020 [29]	Cross-sectional	Iran	693	Children	45.89	WHO	Educational institution	Period	1
Cejudo 2020 [30]	Cross-sectional	Spain	19	Adolescent	42.1	NA	Sport team	Period	12
Yabe 2020a [31]	Cross-sectional	Japan	896	Mixed	67.7	NA	Sport team	Point	NI
Yabe 2020b [32]	Cross-sectional	Japan	566	Mixed	25.62	NA	Sport team	Point	NI
Schwertner 2019 [33]	Cross-sectional	Brazil	330	Adolescent	26	International Obesity Task Force	Educational institution	Lifetime	NI
dos Santos 2019 [34]	Cross-sectional	Brazil	150	Children	49.3	No specific	Educational institution	Lifetime	NI
Aghilinejad 2019 [35]	Cross-sectional	Iran	472	Mixed	57.2	NA	Educational institution	Period	12
Akbar 2019 [36]	Cross-sectional	Kuwait	NI	Adolescent	56.4	WHO	Educational institution	Period	6
Yabe 2019 [37]	Cross-sectional	Japan	NI	Mixed	95.52	NA	Sport team	Point	NI
Noormohamma dpour 2019 [38]	Cross-sectional	Iran	372	Adolescent	0	NA	Educational institution	Lifetime	NI
Angarita-Fonseca 2019 [39]	Cross-sectional	Colombia	73	Children	80.8	NA	Educational institution	Period	1

Azabagic 2019 [40]	Cohort	Bosnia and Herzegovina	1,315	Mixed	49.6	CDC	Educational institution	Point	NI
Muntaner-Mas 2018 [41]	Cross-sectional	Spain	2,032	Children	53.6	International Obesity Task Force	Educational institution	Lifetime	NI
Smith 2017 [42]	Cohort	Australia	1,088	Mixed	47.9	NA	Community	Period	1
Mikkonen 2016 [43]	Cohort	Finland	4,525	Adolescent	43.81	International Obesity Task Force	Community	Period	6
Minghelli 2015 [44]	Cross-sectional	Portugal	966	Mixed	45.2	International Obesity Task Force	Educational institution	Period	12
Minghelli 2014 [45]	Cross-sectional	Portugal	966	Mixed	45.2	International Obesity Task Force	Educational institution	Period	12
Schmidt 2014 [46]	Cross-sectional	Germany	272	Adolescent	58.5	NA	Sport team	Lifetime	NI
Graup 2014 [47]	Cross-sectional	Brazil	1,290	Mixed	49.1	International Obesity Task Force	Educational institution	Lifetime	NI
Silva 2014 [48]	Cross-sectional	Brazil	326	Adolescent	39	International Obesity Task Force	Educational institution	Period	12
Wirth 2013 [49]	Cross-sectional	Switzerland	279	Mixed	45.69	NA	Community	Lifetime	NI
Hershkovich 2013 [50]	Cohort	Israel	805,925	Adolescent	56.65	CDC	Community		NI
Yao 2012 [51]	Control-cases	China	1,214	Mixed	39.7	NA	Educational institution	Period	3
Onofrio 2012 [52]	Cross-sectional	Brazil	1,191	Mixed	36.1	No specific	Educational institution	Period	1

Erne and Elfering 2011 [53]	Cross-sectional	Switzerland	189	Children	45	NA	Educational institution	Period	1
Yao 2011 [54]	Control-cases	China	2,083	Mixed	46.9	NA	Educational institution	Period	3
Balagué 2010 [55]	Cohort	Switzerland	95	Mixed	100	NA	Educational institution and sport team	Lifetime	NI
Mohseni-Bandpei 2007 [56]	Cross-sectional	Iran	4,813	Mixed	47.7	NA	Educational institution	Period	1
Chiang 2006 [57]	Cross-sectional	USA	55	Adolescent	40	NA	Educational institution	Period	0.5
Jones 2005 [58]	Control-cases	England	56	Adolescent	53.57	NA	Educational institution	Point	NI
Korovessis 2005 [59]	Cross-sectional	Greece	1,252	Adolescent	47	NA	Educational institution	Point	NI
Watson 2003 [60]	Cross-sectional	England	849	Mixed	46.1	NA	Educational institution	Period	1
Nissinen 1994 [61]	Cohort	Finland	859	Adolescent	52.5	NA	Educational institution	Period	12

CDC: Centers for Disease Control and Prevention; NA: not applicable; NI: no information; USA: United States of America; WHO: World Health Organization.

Table 2. Prevalence of body mass index, prevalence of low back pain and effect size.

Study	BMI categories prevalence	Prevalence of LBP by BMI category group	OR (95% CI)
Santos 2021 [7]	No categories data	Total: 27.32%	BMI and LBP: 1.07 (0.98–1.17)
Al-Taiar 2020 [28]	Underweight: 1.57% Normal weight: 43.55% Overweight: 21.71% Obesity: 33.16%	Underweight: 25% Normal weight: 19.94% Overweight: 21.21% Obesity: 22.62% Total: 21.18%	Overweight and LBP: 1.08 (0.43-2.72) Obesity and LBP: 1.17 (0.53-2.59)
Rezapur-Shahkolai 2020 [29]	Underweight: 6.78% Normal weight: 67.39% Overweight-obesity: 25.82	Underweight: 27.66% Normal weight: 26.98% Overweight-obesity: 25.14% Total: 26.55%	Overweight-obesity and LBP: 0.88 (0.40-1.94)
Cejudo 2020 [30]	No categories data	Total: 42.1%	BMI and LBP: 2.19 (0.52-9.22)
Yabe 2020a [31]	No categories data	Judo: 6.9% Kendo: 4.7% Karate: 2.9% Total: 4.8%	BMI and LBP: 1.12 (0.85-1.47) judo 1.07 (0.79-1.47) kendo 0.89 (0.40-1.97) karate
Yabe 2020b [32]	No categories data	Total: 9.54%	BMI and LBP: 0.96 (0.70-1.32)
Schwertner 2019 [33]	Underweight: 52.67% Normal weight: 43.33% Overweight: 4%	Underweight: 17.72% Normal weight: 20% Overweight: 50% Total: 37.97%	Overweight and LBP: 4 (0.13-122.74)
dos Santos 2019 [34]	No categories data	Total: 18%	BMI and LBP: 1.18 (1.10-1.26)
Aghilinejad 2019 [35]	Underweight: 5.76% Normal weight: 71.21% Overweight: 17.58% Obese: 5.45%	Underweight: 73.68% Normal weight: 77.02% Overweight: 79.31% Obesity: 72.22% Total: 76.97%	Overweight and LBP: 1.14 (0.28-4.68) Obesity and LBP: 0.78 (0.09-6.78) Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.03 (0.30-3.57)
Akbar 2019 [36]	No categories data	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	Overweight and LBP: 1.20 (0.60-2.40) Obesity and LBP: 0.94 (0.52-1.71)
Yabe 2019 [37]	No categories data	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	BMI and LBP: 1.05 (0.94-1.18)

Noormohammadpour 2019 [38]	No categories data	Total: 46.24%	BMI and LBP: 1.18 (1.10-1.26)
Angarita-Fonseca 2019 [39]	Normal weight: 90.41% Overweight: 9.59%	Normal weight: 36.36% Overweight: 71.4% Total: 39.72%	Overweight and LBP: 1.59 (0.43-5.91)
Azabagic 2019 [40]	Underweight: 4.87% Normal weight: 64.03% Overweight: 18.48% Obesity: 12.62%	Underweight: 32.81% Normal weight: 21.38% Overweight: 22.63% Obesity: 25.9% Total: 22.74%	Overweight and LBP: 1.07 (0.54-2.13) Obesity and LBP: 1.28 (0.59-2.79) Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.16 (0.66-2.03)
Muntaner-Mas 2018 [41]	Underweight: 8.96% Normal weight: 67.57% Overweight-obesity: 23.47%	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.37 (0.87-2.16)
Smith 2017 [42]	No categories data	Total: 32.44%	BMI and LBP: 1.23 (1.20-1.27)
Mikkonen 2016 [43]	Normal weight: 89.26% Obesity: 10.74%	Normal weight: 35.23% Obesity: 37.86% Total: 35.51%	Obesity and LBP: 1.12 (0.76-1.65)
Minghelli 2015 [44]	Underweight: 2.9% Normal weight: 73.29% Overweight: 18.43% Obesity: 5.38%	Underweight:66.67% Normal weight: 46.89% Overweight: 47.19% Obesity: 53.85% Total: 47.2%	Overweight and LBP: 1.01 (0.52-1.21) Obesity and LBP: 1.32 (0.43-4.09) Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.07 (0.59-1.95)
Minghelli 2014 [45]	Underweight: 2.9% Normal weight: 73.29% Overweight: 18.43% Obesity: 5.38%	Underweight:66.67% Normal weight: 46.89% Overweight: 47.19% Obesity: 53.85% Total: 47.2%	Overweight and LBP: 1.01 (0.52-1.21) Obesity and LBP: 1.32 (0.43-4.09) Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.07 (0.59-1.95)
Schmidt 2014 [46]	No categories data	Total: 65.81%	BMI and LBP: 1.62 (1.45-1.80)
Graup 2014 [47]	Normal weight: 73.26% Overweight-obesity: 26.74	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.50 (0.79-2.83)
Silva 2014 [48]	Underweight: 11.96% Normal weight: 72.39% Overweight-obesity: 15.64%	Underweight: 38.46% Normal weight: 58.47% Overweight-obesity: 66.67% Total: 57.36%	Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.42 (0.40-5.08)

Wirth 2013 [49]	No categories data	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	BMI and LBP: 0.98 (0.75-1.29)
Hershkovich 2013 [50]	Underweight: 5.72% Normal weight: 78.08% Overweight: 10.39% Obesity: 5.81%	Underweight: 4.19% Normal weight: 4.21% Overweight: 4.72% Obesity: 5.29% Total: 4.32%	Overweight and LBP: 1.13 (1.06-1.21) Obesity and LBP: 1.29 (1.19-1.40) Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.19 (1.12-1.25)
Yao 2012 [51]	No categories data	Total: 50%	BMI and LBP: 1.13 (1.11-1.16)
Onofrio 2012 [52]	Normal weight: 74.64% Overweight: 19.73% Obesity: 5.62	Normal weight: 13.72% Overweight: 11.49% Obesity: 10.45% Total: 13.1%	Overweight and LBP: 1.00 (0.50-2.00) Obesity and LBP: 0.80 (0.20-3.20) Overweight-obesity and LBP: 0.77 (0.34-1.75)
Erne and Elfering 2011 [53]	No categories data	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	BMI and LBP: 1.19 (0.82-1.72)
Yao 2011 [54]	No categories data	Total: 29.14%	BMI and LBP: 1.22 (1.20-1.24)
Balagué 2010 [55]	No categories data	Total: 34.74%	BMI and LBP: 2.30 (1.69-3.13)
Mohseni-Bandpei 2007 [56]	No categories data	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	BMI and LBP: 0.89 (0.38-2.10)
Chiang 2006 [57]	No categories data	Total: 34.54%	BMI and LBP: 0.72 (0.43-1.21)
Jones 2005 [58]	No categories data	Total: 50%	BMI and LBP: 4.25 (2.56-7.05)
Korovessis 2005 [59]	No categories data	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	BMI and LBP: 1.11 (0.93-1.33)
Watson 2003 [60]	Normal weight: 69.14% Overweight-obesity: 30.86%	Normal weight: 24.02% Overweight-obesity: 24.43% Total: 24.15%	Overweight-obesity and LBP: 1.02 (0.52-2.01)
Nissinen 1994 [61]	No categories data	No prevalence data, effect size contributed directly	BMI and LBP: 1.00 (0.67-1.49)

BMI: Body Mass Index; LBP: Low Back Pain; CI: Confidence Interval; OR: Odds Ratio

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